

The EXPLORE Platform for Innovative Scientific Data Exploration and Exploitation Applications for Space Sciences

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Abstract.

The EXPLORE platform is a bespoke platform build to serve the development and deployment of the EXPLORE project's scientific data applications for the exploration and exploitation of space science data. It has evolved into a versatile science platform adopting the "bring-the-user-to-the-data-and-tools" paradigm. It offers a range of functionalities including an application catalogue, an application deployment dashboard, a space browser, private workspaces and an administrative dashboard for user management, access control, and resource management. It is a flexibly modular system to deploy many types of containerised applications in the web browser and is itself easily deployed on other infrastructures.

1. Introduction

This paper presents the EXPLORE platform¹, a web platform developed as part of the *Innovative Scientific Data Exploration and Exploitation Applications for Space Sciences* (EXPLORE) project funded by the EU Horizon 2020 Research & Innovation programme. This platform supports the development, testing, and demonstration of the suite of scientific data applications (Apps) for lunar exploration and galactic and stellar science that are the main objective of the EXPLORE project, which aims to promote scientific exploitation of planetary and astrophysical space science data.

EXPLORE is part of a broader landscape of open science platforms and initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud (Schoupe 2018), ESA Datalabs (Arviset et al. 2021) and ESCAPE Science Analysis Platform (Allen et al. 2022). Our ambition is to support and accelerate space science exploration and exploitation with open data and open science, promoting the uptake and sustainability of novel applications and science platforms.

2. EXPLORE platform

The core objective of the EXPLORE science platform is to have a system capable of deploying and running instances (in the web browser) of scientific data applications pro-

¹<https://explore-platform.eu>

vided by the different scientific software development teams in the EXPLORE project. The design paradigm of the EXPLORE platform, like most modern science platforms, is to bring the user to the data and tools, rather than bringing the tools and data to the user.

All-together, the EXPLORE platform consists of the following components, some of which are discussed in more detail in the next sections.

- Static pages
- Blog posts
- User workspace
- Space browser (planetary archive search form)
- App catalogue
- App deployment dashboard
- Admin dashboard:
 - user and group management system
 - Access Control List (ACL) system
 - App moderation & inspection
 - Resource management

2.1. User workspace

In the EXPLORE design (registered) users have access to archive data, either directly through the file-system or via the platform applications. Data is stored remotely, either on the platform infrastructure or in remote repositories that are accessed through external APIs. Users can store data to their private workspace. They can either upload their own data, save data directly from the different available applications or through the archive search form (aka ‘space browser’).

2.2. Space browser

The space browser provides a search tool for scientific data for a selected number of planetary missions to the Moon, Mars and Mercury. Users can define a search area by drawing a region on the map as well as enter search parameter constraints. Data are retrieved using external APIs and can be previewed (if previews are available), downloaded or saved to the user workspace.

2.3. App catalogue

The App catalogue view is used to search among the different public or shared applications. Users can immediately start their preferred application which will open in a new browser tab.

2.4. App deployment dashboard

One important feature of the EXPLORE platform is that it gives (approved) developers a way to deploy applications (packaged as a Docker image) on the platform and make them available to the users. The platform provides developers a streamlined process to deploy, test, and share their (containerised) applications. Developers can link their application to shared datasets (that they upload to the platform), define meta-data, set environment variables, and assign minimum resource requirements (e.g. RAM, CPU).

2.5. Admin dashboard

Lastly, to manage the different aspects of the platform, such as computing resources, user and group permissions, and the applications, there is an integrated administration dashboard. Platform administrators have fine-grained control of user permissions (e.g. for updating and running SDAs) and user quota using Access Control Lists (ACLs). The administrators can also test applications before approving them to be made publicly accessible to other users.

3. EXPLORE Scientific Data Applications

Scientific data applications are effectively containerised applications which expose a user-interface to a defined port. Currently the system is based on Docker technology. To deploy an application the developer only needs to provide the URL to the Docker image (for example a GitLab registry), set configuration options (private/public, minimal resources needed), add metadata key-value pairs, and, optionally, set environment variables and data mount points.

To facilitate interoperability and sustainability of the EXPLORE scientific data applications, we defined a common (open) design to create applications contained in a single Docker image. This design can serve as a blue-print for future applications to be deployed on the EXPLORE or other science platforms.

In our concept we make a distinction between a ‘single-service’ and a ‘multi-service’ application. A ‘single-service’ application is useful to create, for example, interactive web applications that connect front-end user interface events to running Python code (e.g. with Bokeh or Plotly/Dash). The ‘multi-service’ framework is used to integrate different science, AI, and visualisation modules that are each connected using APIs (e.g. Flask or FastAPI) and an Asynchronous Server Gateway Interface (ASGI) such as uvicorn or gunicorn. The modules are load balanced / proxied via a proxy, such as NGINX, and served via an user interface to the platform user.

We note that although in principle any kind of application - with or without a scientific purpose - can be deployed on the platform, the actual scope of pertinent applications is set by the platform administrator who needs to approve each application before it can be started. Furthermore, developer permissions can be granted only to trusted users.

An in-depth presentation of the (open-source) scientific data applications developed by EXPLORE falls outside the scope of this contribution. Novel concepts for collaborative and guided visual analytics of astrophysical and planetary data in the context of EXPLORE are presented in Rauch et al. (2023).

4. Conclusions

The EXPLORE platform is a bespoke solution for the challenges of the EXPLORE project to develop a series of scientific data applications for different space science communities, from galactic, to stellar and lunar researchers.

The platform's modular design allows for straightforward adaptation and customisation to other (scientific) disciplines. It can be easily deployed elsewhere with minimal requirements² on the hosting infrastructure. The low technical and cost hurdle could be particularly interesting for research groups or (international) collaborations. The platform operator has full control on who is allowed access. Advanced access control allows for fine-grained user access to applications, data and computing resources.

The scientific data application designs allow for 'single' and 'multi' service applications and can be used as a starting point for future scientific applications that are developed for deployment on science platforms.

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²sizing depends mainly on the number of expected simultaneous running instances and computing resources assigned to those instances